

A distributed data-mining software platform for
extreme data across the compute continuum

D5.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Community Building Report

Version 1.0

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Introduction	6
2.1. Structure of the Document	6
2.2. Aim, Scope and Objectives.....	6
2.3. Work Package Context and Motivation	7
3. Communication Plan	8
3.1. Target Audience and Key Messages.....	8
3.2. Branding and Project Identity	10
3.2.1. Corporate Image.....	10
3.2.2. Logo	10
3.2.3. Typography	12
3.2.4. Language	12
3.2.5. Project Templates	12
3.2.6. Website.....	15
3.2.7. Social Media	16
3.2.8. Equality and Diversity.....	16
4. Initial Dissemination Plan.....	17
4.1. Dissemination Objectives	17
4.2. Dissemination Tools and Channels.....	18
4.2.1. Website (https://extract-project.eu)	18
4.2.2. Social networks: Twitter and LinkedIn	19
4.2.3. Dissemination Pack.....	20
4.2.4. Publications.....	20
4.2.5. Press Strategy.....	21
4.3. Dissemination Events	22
4.3.1. Workshops	23
4.4. Dissemination register	23
5. Community Building and Training Activities	24
5.1. Synergies.....	24
5.2. Internal Trainings	25

5.3 External Trainings.....	26
6. Initial Exploitation Plan	26
6.1. Preliminary Plan for Key Exploitable Results (KERs).....	28
6.2. Preliminary Exploration of Tools for Exploitation of KERs.....	28
7. Initial Sustainability Vision.....	29
8. Evaluation of Dissemination and Communication Performance	30
Table 5 EXTRACT project dissemination, community building, exploitation and sustainability key project indicators.....	31
9. Conclusion.....	31
10. Acronyms and abbreviations	32
11. Annex 1: Dissemination Register.....	33

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable defines the dissemination and communication, community building, exploitation and sustainability strategies of the EXTRACT project. The EXTRACT project addresses the topic of HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 by integrating the edge, cloud and HPC technologies to improve data mining methods on extremely large and constantly growing, sparse, dispersed and heterogeneous data. To do so, the project will implement a distributed data-mining software platform that will facilitate the development of complex data-mining workflows effectively and efficiently addressing extreme data to optimise decision-making. Throughout the life of the project, this platform's main features and its application via the project's two use cases will be highlighted and shared with the identified target audiences with the goal of raising awareness of the project and establishing a community around the project and its results. The platform features to be highlighted include:

1. enhanced data infrastructure, AI and big-data frameworks to facilitate the development of unified data-mining workflows describing extreme data characteristics, data processes and analytics methods;
2. data-driven orchestration mechanisms that, based on the workflow description, can deploy and schedule data processes and analytics methods across the compute continuum, fulfilling extreme data characteristics;
3. integration and interoperability of multiple computing technologies into a unified and secure compute continuum, featuring the most suitable computing elements, i.e., HPC, edge and cloud computing resources, to effectively address the extreme data diverse characteristics;
4. cybersecurity and digital privacy mechanisms across all software layers, i.e., from data integrity/protection and secure Machine Learning (ML) models, down to trusted computation and secured communication.

To contextualise the initial dissemination, exploitation and community building plan for the EXTRACT project, the second chapter of the deliverable provides a summary of the objectives of Work Package 5 (WP5, Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability) and the structure of the document. This is followed by Chapter 3, the introduction to the communication plan, which identifies and describes the different types of target audiences that the project seeks to communicate with and key messages for each of them. It also describes the visual identity of the project, namely the logo and presentation templates, and the main communication channels, including the project website and social networks. The launch of the public website represents a major milestone for the project. It acts as the main communication and dissemination channel and offers detailed information about the project, the consortium, research publications, news, events and public deliverables related to the project.

Chapter 4 elaborates on the dissemination strategy by describing its purpose, the tools used to successfully deploy it and the necessary steps to be applied during the three years of the project. A brochure (in digital format) and a poster (in digital format) will be made available to the consortium members to ease the dissemination of the project in events, conferences and symposiums. Chapter 5 of the deliverable goes on to

address the steps that will be taken to build a community around the project by proposing synergies, trainings, workshops, and activities that will attract a specific audience who can apply and build on the results of the project. As defined in the deliverable, it is planned to have 1 internal training per year that will set the tone for the external trainings, which will include 1 workshop, 1 tutorial, and 1 Hackathon. These training events will act as a capacity building exercise for the consortium and set the foundation for external trainings about the technology being developed within the project. Additionally, the project will organise a final event with significant attendance to provide a space for sharing final results and networking opportunities that will help ensure the sustainability of the project. The last section details the key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the dissemination, communication, and exploitation performance of the project.

The deliverable sets out to share the dissemination plan and proposes a cohesive way of communicating information. It also ensures that all members of the consortium understand the purpose of dissemination, community building, exploitation and project sustainability and the messages that will help reach the different audiences.

While it is a bit early to report any meaningful results on exploitation and sustainability activities at this stage, this document also outlines the main principles, tools and ideas that the consortium has planned for exploitation and sustainability.

Exploitation activities have a broader scope than that of communication and dissemination. They can include actions such as using the project results in research activities that go beyond those covered by the EXTRACT project; developing, creating and marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service. Exploitation can only start once the research results are available. It focuses on making concrete use of research results for commercial, societal, policy, and other purposes. We address the preliminary planning for exploitation in [Chapter 6](#).

Sustainability refers to the exploitation of results after the end of the project. Task 5.4 will rely both on the results of the project, and on the work of Task 5.2 Building communities, to make recommendations on results' exploitation after M36. For example partners could leverage the expertise of SixSq in selling business applications, designed to run at the edge and/or in the cloud, on the Nuvla Marketplace. An exploratory phase around the marketplace platform and functionalities will give partners time to imagine what the EXTRACT marketplace could look like. For example, this dedicated marketplace can be hosted by Nuvla, as a spin-off. We address the Sustainability preliminary planning in [Chapter 7](#).

2. Introduction

Communicating and disseminating the project's results and defining opportunities for exploitation and community building is a priority for the EXTRACT consortium. A clear and well-designed plan improves the reach and effectiveness of project results. The first six months of the WP5 within the EXTRACT project have been devoted to setting up the project's visual identity, identifying and understanding project stakeholders, and crafting a community building and dissemination plan that will set the tone for the entire life-cycle of the project. This deliverable, 5.1 Dissemination, exploitation, and community building report, will provide a description of the activities performed in the first period of the project (until month 6) and detail dissemination, community building, and exploitation plans for month 6 - month 36.

This deliverable represents one of three dissemination, exploitation, sustainability and community building reports that will be prepared throughout the life of the project (months 6, 15 and 36, respectively). It focuses on initial steps to build awareness of the project, its motivation and objectives. It also suggests activities for the entirety of the project, as well as specific measurable indicators that will ensure the plan is developing as planned. Subsequent reports will focus on monitoring how the plan unfolds, building interaction between the project and target groups and ensuring uptake of project results.

2.1. Structure of the Document

This deliverable is divided into eight parts. It first provides information about the aim, scope and objectives of WP5. It then details the communication ([Chapter 3](#)), dissemination ([Chapter 4](#)), community building and training ([Chapter 5](#)) plans needed to fulfil the objectives of EXTRACT project. It then elaborates on the activities that facilitate the commercialisation and exploitation of the resulting platform, innovation and results ([Chapter 6](#)). The initial sustainability vision appears in [Chapter 7](#). The deliverable concludes with [Chapter 8](#), which defines the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to evaluate the success of the objectives set out in these plans and to increase the effectiveness of the WP activities.

2.2. Aim, Scope and Objectives

This deliverable elaborates a first version of the plan with the actions that are expected to be performed to communicate, disseminate and exploit the outcomes of the EXTRACT project. It offers information on the strategy to establish and maintain online, off-line and hybrid presence, and the implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation tools to promote stakeholder engagement.

To ensure that EXTRACT project results reach a variety of target audiences that can benefit from them, key messages and channels have been identified for each audience and as has a strategy for dissemination activities that reach these audiences and

amplifies this message. In the first six months of the project, the WP5 team laid the framework for the creation of a cohesive brand and dissemination channels and tools that will allow us to reach the defined target audiences in the best way. It has also identified actions needed to identify and build a committed community around project results from the beginning of the project and beyond.

To fulfil this aim, the plan:

- Identifies a list of potential stakeholders.
- Describes the design, launch and maintenance of the dedicated project website.
- Introduces the project's social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn).
- Presents the project dissemination material that will set the tone for the project and define channels through which to reach the identified target audiences (templates, brochures, posters).
- Identifies potential participation in industrial and academic forums and venues.
- Remains open to other activities that might be relevant to achieve the objectives of the project and ensure the proper quality of the outcomes.
- Proposes an initial training plan and suggests some opportunities for community building.
- Provides early ideas, planning and identification of potential exploitable results and exploitation avenues.
- Provides early vision about the sustainability of the project, during project's lifespan and, more importantly, after its successful conclusion.
- Defines a set of KPIs that will allow the WP5 team to monitor progress, evaluate the success of the plan in relation to the initial aim, and ensure the plan stays focused on the project goal.

In addition to the WP5 lead partner (BINARE, BIN) and core WP5 task leads (Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), SIXSQ, BIN), all partners will contribute to the promotion of the project through their own websites, social media and other communication and marketing channels, and activities (e.g., potential presence at expos and conferences).

2.3. Work Package Context and Motivation

Work package 5 on Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability is responsible for:

1. **Fostering adoption** of results providing training activities to relevant stakeholders.
2. **Maximising** project impact through dissemination in related communities.
3. **Creating** a community of interest around project results from the early stages.
4. **Ensuring IP is duly managed** according to Horizon Europe (HE) regulations.
5. **Identifying key exploitable results (KERs) and innovations** and preparing appropriate exploitation plan in line with market needs.
6. **Providing** a long-term sustainability plan for EXTRACT technology.

WP5 is transversal and ensures two-way communication with other consortium members to ensure that they are informed of dissemination requirements, target audiences and messaging. It also helps members identify and share their results in a coordinated and transparent way. Moreover, it explores interactive engagement means with the general public and the relevant research and industry communities.

3. Communication Plan

This section presents the initial communication plan, which focuses on raising awareness of the EXTRACT project among the identified target audiences. The plan details the specific actions needed to facilitate the understanding of the project and foster the engagement of stakeholders that might be interested in the results. For that purpose, social network accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter) and a website have been created, along with several sections aimed at publishing the news, events, and communication material related to the project.

3.1. Target Audience and Key Messages

Table 1 EXTRACT project target audiences and key messages

Target audience	Key messages	Value to target audiences	Abstraction level	Channels
Research community	New cutting-edge scientific and technical results in major conferences and journals on 1) data infrastructures & AI-embedded semantic and staging engines, 2) data mining frameworks, 3) data-driven orchestration & monitoring from edge-cloud-HPC continuum addressing extreme data requirements, 4) data & continuum cybersecurity, 5) advanced AI algorithms for decision-making; open data sets (NenuFAR observations on EOSC) and source code SW	<p>Researchers can build on EXTRACT scientific results and reuse generated datasets to pursue their own lines of research.</p> <p>The open-source platform components can also be used for extreme data mining in different research domains (e.g., astronomy, bioinformatics, high-energy physics)</p>	Very detailed technical information; well-documented source code; re-usable, semantically annotated datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Website – Social media – Specialized technical and research events – Peer-reviewed publications in journals, conferences, workshops

	components will be made available			
Industrial community	<p>Openly available EXTRACT technological assets:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Highly programmable, interoperable and secure frameworks for the easy development of data mining workflows across the continuum, 2) scalable, fast, distributed extreme data processing mechanisms, 3) Holistic data/ cybersecurity layer for the complete data mining lifecycle, 4) Marketplace for EXTRACT data mining workflows (i.e., data processes and analytics) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) New business opportunities and markets by shifting existing solutions into a technology that supported edge-to-cloud- to HPC continuum to address extreme data characteristics, 2) Potential of increasing trustworthiness and security, 3) Easier creation of complex data mining workflows for vertical domains, 4) cost and energy efficient continuum utilization based on intelligent orchestration and monitoring. 	<p>Technical information overview, focused on impact and market opportunities, quantifiable performance and cost enhancement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Website – Social media – Events – Press releases – Journals
Policymakers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Innovative data-driven and human-centric solution for: crisis management & smart-cities, enhanced space-weather modelling, etc. 2) Strengthen European data analytics capacity, 3) Leverage European data sources, i.e., Copernicus, Galileo, EOSC, 4) promote use of energy-efficiency edge computing, 5) European multi-disciplinary with 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Opening up opportunities to enhance European competitiveness in new market, 2) Strengthen Europe's leadership in edge/cloud/ HPC computing and data analytics capacity, 3) Societal impact and enhanced citizen trust in digital transformation/ crisis management, 	<p>Socio-economic impact and market opportunities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Website – Social media – Events – Press releases

	academia-in-industry collaboration	4) Reduced carbon footprint thanks to edge computing		
General public	<p>1) New research and business opportunities will lead to the creation of highly skilled jobs,</p> <p>2) personalized evacuation applications, enhancing safety,</p> <p>3) higher technological engagement of the greater public (e.g., access to high-quality astronomy images, highly programmable frameworks to be used in education, etc.)</p>	<p>1) European public investment leading to concrete solutions that will bring new business opportunities and added value to society and science,</p> <p>2) Increased trust in administration in crisis management,</p> <p>3) increased awareness of the impacts of the data-driven technologies in the way toward digitalization of society</p>	High-level abstraction, mapping into general concepts and scenarios, targeting different age groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Website – Social media – Events – Press release

3.2. Branding and Project Identity

3.2.1. Corporate Image

A common graphic identity in all dissemination activities allows for better visibility, recognition and branding of the project. All communication and dissemination material will include the name of the project, the website, the EU acknowledgement, and the graphic elements described in this section, such as the logo. The brand of the EXTRACT project includes its corporate image, brand and style. The project brand guide has been shared with all partners to ensure coherence and consistency and can be found in the internal project repository. This brand guide defines the proper use of the logo, the project colours, typography and language.

3.2.2. Logo

The EXTRACT logo comes in different formats:

- **Logo with the whole name of the project:** this logo will be used the most prevalent in the beginning with the aim of building a brand and ensuring that the name and purpose of the project is present.
- **Logo with URL:** this logo will be used more once the project is recognized by the regular target audiences and content has been created and uploaded to the website.

- **Standalone logo:** this logo may be used on promotional material when printed small and once the brand is more established.
- **Symbol:** the symbol can be used on promotional material when printed small and once the brand is more established.

Figure 1 Different formats of the EXTRACT logo

The logo shows the shortage of the protect name, 'A distributed data-mining software platform for **EXTR**eme data **AC**ross the compu**TE** continuum'. The logo seeks to suggest that the A is being 'extracted', thus playing on the word 'extract' and highlighted the 'ACT' as if encouraging action through extracting data and suggesting a spatial element. Blue is the main colour. It is associated with technology and innovation.

All EXTRACT partners have approved the EXTRACT logo. A brand guide, with all the logo formats and indications for their use, has been sent to all partners and is available on the project's internal repository. Partners have been informed of the importance of including the project logo, the EU logo and EU acknowledgement on all project documentation, and ideally in colour. All formats of this logo are available on the

branding page of the project website, on the internal project repository and in [Section 3.2.2](#).

3.2.3. Typography

The font defined for the EXTRACT logo is Eart Orbiter-extra bold, which has a sharp edge and space vibe as a nod to the space use case. Complementary typographies include Krona one regular and Verdana.

Verdana is the recommended font for all editable materials (deliverables, posters, presentations, etc.) because it is available on most computers.

3.2.4. Language

The official language of the EXTRACT project is British English (BE). However, dissemination material should be translated into the different languages within the consortium, where possible. Each partner should ensure that the materials are adequately translated into the local languages, e.g., in the case of the press releases for the local media. Funding for this is not included in the dissemination budget.

3.2.5. Project Templates

A set of templates have been designed for use in the activities of the EXTRACT project to strengthen its visual identity.

3.2.5.1. Presentation/Slides Template

The presentation template is to be used for all presentations done by all partners. It is available in the internal repository for all partners to use. The presentation template is available in both Microsoft PowerPoint and Open Office. This template gives some design guidelines, as well as a general-purpose EXTRACT PowerPoint content template that can be incorporated into other presentations to disseminate the project and its results.

Figure 2 EXTRACT presentation/slide template

3.2.5.2. Poster Template

The poster template has been created in PowerPoint and can be used as a base template for poster presentations in different events. It is a basic layout that partners can fill in with different scientific and technical content depending on the presentation objective and audience. It has been included in the internal repository for all partners to use.

Figure 3 EXTRACT poster template

3.2.5.3. Roll-up Banner Template

A roll-up banner will be designed for use in various dissemination activities including conferences, booths, and the proposed final event. A roll-up banner is an effective way to draw attention to a specific booth or stand within a large expo setting, and it provides a professional and sleek look for events organised as part of the EXTRACT project.

3.2.5.4. Deliverable Template

A template for all deliverables with the logo and its structure is available on the internal project repository and has been sent to all project partners. The font used is Verdana font.

Figure 4 EXTRACT project deliverable template

3.2.5.5. Virtual Background Template

EXTRACT partners are often involved in external teleconferences where they present EXTRACT findings, including teleconferences, webinars, among others. A background template has been created for use for these activities.

Figure 5 EXTRACT project virtual background

3.2.6. Website

The project website, available since the first weeks of the project, is hosted at <https://extract-project.eu>. The dissemination team at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) is responsible for the construction, maintenance, and hosting of the website.

The website has been designed as a multi-device experience that works well across different device types: PCs, tablets and mobile phones. The website will integrate any multimedia material, such as social media accounts and videos, as well as acting as the external repository of public project related activities (events, news, approved deliverables, publications).

Figure 6 Screenshot of a section of the EXTRACT project website

The website seeks to:

- Provide a source of technical information to a variety of audiences, including technical details via news pieces, deliverables and academic papers that will be made available during the project.
- Share news and updates to reflect the activity of the project and demonstrate an active community.
- Encourage interaction by inviting its audience to get involved in the project, through participation in events, watching videos, or similar material, if deemed appropriate.

The dissemination team is responsible for editing the website content, website deliverables, feedback and statistics.

Access statistics will be monitored using Google Analytics. This information will help to improve the content and structure of the site, as well as having more information about the target audiences.

3.2.7. Social Media

While the project website acts as the main reference point for sharing information about the project, social media will also be used to raise awareness of the project's goals and activities and to drive interest to the website. Social media is also beneficial for raising awareness of the project to broader audiences and potential stakeholders.

Currently, the following social media channels have been established:

- LinkedIn: <https://linkedin.com/company/extract-eu-project/>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/EXTRACT_EU_proj

As the world's largest professional networking site, LinkedIn offers an excellent way of connecting with industry, academics and the general public. The EXTRACT LinkedIn page will be used to post news and information about the project's participation in events. The goal is to share technical discussions with industry-related stakeholders to engage with the project. LinkedIn activity is monitored via LinkedIn Analytics, which show general information on followers, visitors, and visitor demographics, such as their sector background.

To have access to networking on the go and communicate with everyone in real-time, an EXTRACT Twitter account will be used. Twitter will be used as a platform to create synergies with other similar stakeholders and influencers to boost the impact of the project's dissemination activities. Through this channel the objective is to reach academia and, if possible, industry. Twitter Analytics will provide information about the account's performance and analyse the effect of and reaction to different communication activities, which will help improve our future actions.

3.2.8. Equality and Diversity

The EXTRACT project is committed to contributing to equal opportunities and diversity and supporting the European Commission's promotion of the visibility and inclusion of different groups.

To ensure the EXTRACT project reflects a community where all talents can thrive and integrate into the project, the consortium is committed to participating in the [three main levels of gender equality addressed in Horizon Europe](#). These include, having partner Gender Equality Plans publicly available on the project website, integrating a gender dimension into the project, and increasing gender balance throughout the project. While the project's project management reports on the latter, the WP5 team seeks to raise awareness of scientists that come from diverse backgrounds.

With this in mind, WP5 will monitor and participate in equality and diversity campaigns, such as Feb 11-*Women in Science Day*, 8M *International Women's Day*, *European Diversity Month*, among others. More information on the social media campaigns undertaken within the first six months of the project related to these events can be found in [Section 4.2.2.1](#). These campaigns reflect the project's solidarity with the values behind these activities and demonstrate to our target audience that the project values and promotes equality and diversity. Moreover, WP5 will work to ensure that the women in the project have a platform and the support to share their findings and communicate their successes. Specifically, we will pursue a 'Women in STEM' interview series on the news section of the project website to highlight the work done by the women in the project.

4. Initial Dissemination Plan

4.1. Dissemination Objectives

To efficiently reach the targets for dissemination and to maximize the visibility of the project and its results, WP5 will employ the above-mentioned communication tools to reach the target audiences, as detailed in [Table 1](#) (*EXTRACT project target audiences and key messages*). The following objectives drive the dissemination strategy:

- To make the findings of the EXTRACT project known as widely as feasible, especially among researchers, stakeholders and general public.
- To contribute to the advertisement of EXTRACT dissemination activities, including background information, working papers, workshops, conferences, and trainings to keep the community informed.
- To enhance the impact of EXTRACT and engage with standard bodies, technology and service providers, and technology uptakers.
- To facilitate and enable a close collaboration between inter-disciplinary community of stakeholders, encompassing technology providers, public and standard bodies, research and innovation organisations across Europe.

The dissemination strategy will consist of three main stages that loosely coincide with each year of the project: raising awareness, community building, and encouraging the use of project results. Each stage will require tools and messages that evolve depending on the status of the project and the success of the strategy in each stage.

1. Stage One: Raising Awareness

In the first stage of the project, the WP5 team will ensure a cohesive project identity. Project partners will present the project, specifically its vision, goals, and the consortium wherever possible. Partners will also seek out projects and stakeholders with similar goals and interests to build a community around the project's technology.

2. Stage Two: Community Building

In the second stage of the project, the consortium will seek to increase its participation in conferences, workshops and trainings. Partners will share more in-depth information on the technologies created as part of the project and their applications. Specific emphasis will be placed on explaining the different project technologies to provide stakeholders with a deep understanding of the project technologies to help amplify the project results.

3. Stage Three: Encourage use of project results

Toward the end of the project, partners will work with stakeholders to ensure uptake of technologies to ensure project sustainability. Tutorials, industry events and partnerships within the established EXTRACT community and beyond will help ensure the dissemination and applicability of project results.

4.2. Dissemination Tools and Channels

Addressing the varied target audiences defined in [Table 1](#) and beyond, requires employing various dissemination tools and channels. Each tool and channel offer the opportunity to directly provide these audiences with messages that are tailored to them and that reach them via their preferred medium.

The public website is the first point of contact and plays a significant role in dissemination. Scientific and industrial conferences, the project dissemination pack, a press strategy and scientific publications are also used to increase the awareness of technical and non-technical audiences.

4.2.1. Website (<https://extract-project.eu>)

The project website will provide the most up-to-date public information about the project. In the first six months of the project, the website was launched and shared with project partners and other EU-funded projects via press release with the goal of raising awareness about the project. From month six on, the website will also include upcoming events, publications, public deliverables, videos and a news page that is updated monthly.

Starting in month six, project partners will begin to contribute with monthly texts about their specific work within the context of the project. An editorial plan has been developed by the WP5 team to provide guidance to partners regarding this contribution. The expected text is intended to be technical but accessible and offer each partner the chance to explain their work, their progress and any preliminary findings. This, and the monthly updating of the news section by WP5 with news on dissemination activities will ensure that the website remains engaging and informative.

4.2.2. Social networks: Twitter and LinkedIn

While the project website acts as the main reference point for sharing information about the project, the project will also use social media to raise awareness of the project's goals and activities, and to drive interest to the website. Social media is also beneficial for raising awareness of the project to broader audiences and potential stakeholders. By joining the greater conversation, the project has more opportunities to create interest in its results, join communities of like-minded projects, and access different types of audiences. It is important to note, that while these networks offer the opportunity to amplify the project's message, they are no substitute for the substantial message and interface provided by the website or other dissemination channels like events and publications. Instead, they intend to provide impetus to the work being done and to drive action, either back to the project website where in-depth information is available, or to encourage participation in events or workshops.

4.2.2.1. Social media campaigns

Participating in social media campaigns focused on women in science, diversity, AI, astronomy, disaster awareness, HPC, and more, help the project engage with different stakeholders. It is an opportunity to highlight certain features or researchers in the project and to emphasize the values of the project.

Since the project's inception, the EXTRACT project has participated in social media campaigns regarding the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11 February) and International Women's Day (8 March). The post on 11 February provided a platform to highlight an interview given by a female researcher from the EXTRACT project in the HiPEAC Vision magazine. There were many engagements due to this campaign and the project's followers grew following this campaign. For 8M, the project took the opportunity to express its solidarity with women and to 'Embrace Equality', this year's slogan. While no project results were disseminated, this activity drew visitors to the website for more information about the project. These campaigns will be updated and employed in the years to come, as will others related to the project technology (AI, ML, digital twin).

The EXTRACT consortium has been informed of the benefits of using social media to disseminate the project's activities, and partners who are active on these social media channels are happy to help disseminate news, updates, dissemination material, videos, etc. on their own social media channels focusing on Twitter and LinkedIn.

We also engage on social media with other projects under our Cluster, [BDVA](#), and [AI-on-Demand Platform](#), and [AI-Data-Robotics-Association \(ADRA\)](#).

Finally, we will also ask the EC Project Officer to help us disseminate EXTRACT project-related news on their own social media channels and news services.

4.2.3. Dissemination Pack

Basic dissemination material for use by the consortium are being developed to facilitate partners' ability to quickly, uniformly, and properly (correct acknowledgement and branding) produce materials that will help them be ready for dissemination activities, including:

- **Flyer:** The general flyer will provide information about the EXTRACT project, its objectives, impact for society, and practical usage through the use cases. The flyer will be uploaded on the Branding section of the website and on the project's internal repository so that project partners can easily download and print it for their own dissemination purposes. It will be distributed at events.
- **Poster:** A general overview poster will be developed to be used by all partners. The first version of the poster will include a general description of the project and its aims, as well as the use cases and a brief description of the technology. The poster will be periodically updated as the first results are published and will be used in all events where EXTRACT participates. It will be uploaded on the project's internal repository.
- **Overview presentation:** A presentation with a general overview of the project has been designed. It will be used by all partners in dissemination activities in which the project needs to be presented for the first time to an audience. This presentation is useful to transmit the project's objectives and key messages in an aligned fashion, regardless of the presenter. The presentation will be periodically updated if needed. Along with the rest of the dissemination material, the presentation will be uploaded on the EXTRACT internal repository.
- **Videos:** Understanding that our society is increasingly consuming information by visual means, the dissemination team will produce videos during the project, in English with subtitles in local languages. Developing of this video is an engaging and informative means of communicating the project's results, aims, and applications. All partners will contribute to disseminate the videos. They will be widely shared with the partners, technical media, and other online channels.

4.2.4. Publications

The consortium is committed to OpenScience and FAIR data principles. It will seek to ensure that all EXTRACT results are based on open, cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and as widely possible in the research process. WP5 has prepared a set of publication guidelines to ensure that the consortium is informed of OpenScience requirements and will monitor dissemination activities to ensure that reportable results comply with them.

Scientific publications will be immediate OpenAccess and deposited in a trusted repository. All EXTRACT publications will include the following sentence:

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under the EXTRACT project, grant agreement number 101093110.

The following publication procedure has been defined and shared with consortium partners:

1. The authors submit the publication for peer review, and as soon as possible after the submission (at most 45 days), the co-authors share the submission.
2. One of the authors sends an email to the whole consortium, notifying the project partners about the submission.
3. The partners have 90 days to review the publication and raise objections, if any.
4. If the objection is valid, the submission is retracted. If there are no objections, the submission moves forward.
5. If the publication is accepted, one of the authors must send the publication and all related information to the Dissemination WP leaders with the rest of the authors in cc at least 30 days before the camera-ready.
6. Dissemination WP leaders will then give feedback and validate that everything is correct.
7. After the camera-ready, the Dissemination WP Leader will add the information about the publication on the project website and the dissemination register.
8. Each partner is responsible for entering its publications into the EC Participant Portal once published and ensuring that the publication is available in a recognised repository upon acceptance.

4.2.5. Press Strategy

The press strategy will be consistent with the dissemination strategy and its objectives. Press releases are an effective way of communicating the existence of the EXTRACT project to the technical media and their corresponding audience (see [Table 1](#) on target audiences). Press releases attract attention to the project's progress and its achievements. Press releases will be launched throughout the life of the project.

The initial press release, launched on 3 March 2023, was met with success. It received attention from prominent technical media and social media. The press release explained EXTRACT project objectives, partners, and practical use cases. Subsequent press releases will be issued throughout the project to highlight certain activities, raise awareness of findings, or announce specific participations. A final press release will be launched at the end of the project to wrap up the work and present the final results.

All press releases will be included in the EXTRACT news page and media mentions will be included in the press clipping page. All partners have the opportunity to include them on their institutional websites (example: partner BSC on its [institutional website](#)) to increase the click rates and referrals. In addition, all partners have been encouraged to write a press article about EXTRACT to be shared with local media channels. All

partners are encouraged to translate the press releases in their national language and share it with local media channels.

4.3. Dissemination Events

Another important dissemination channel includes attendance to and presentations at high-level peer-reviewed conferences in the field of HPC, Internet of Things, embedded systems, computer design, automation, and machine learning/AI, crisis management, space, among others. Presenting the latest updates of the project at such events, meetings or workshops will be an effective means of involving academic and industry leaders in technological discussions early on. The list of targeted academic/industrial events includes conferences and networks of excellence.

Table 2 includes an indicative list of events that EXTRACT partners could potentially participate in. Most of these are regular annual events and we plan to continue to identify additional events throughout the project.

Event Information	Date and Location
BDVA Data Week 2023	June 13 – 15, 2023 / Luleå, Sweden
ICML (International conference on Machine Learning)	July 23-29 2023- Honolulu, Hawaii
SIGKDD (Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining)	August 6-10 2023 - Long Beach, CA, USA
VLDB (Very Large Data Bases Conference)	August 28-September 1, 2023- Vancouver, Canada
CIKM (Conference on Information and Knowledge management)	October 2023- Birmingham, UK
ECAI (European Conference on Artificial Intelligence)	October 1-6 2023 - Kraków, Poland
EBDVF (European Big Data Value Forum)	October 25-27, 2023, Valencia, Spain
HiPEAC Workshop	January 17-19, Munich, Germany
ICDE (40th IEEE International Conference on Data Engineering)	April 16 2024- Utrecht, Netherlands
EENA Conference	April 24-26, 2024, Valencia, Spain
Transportation Research Arena 2024	April 15 – 18, 2024, Dublin, Ireland
IoT Solution World Congress (world’s largest IoT event series)	May 21-23, 2024 - Barcelona, Spain

AAMAS (International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems)	May 2024 – Auckland, New Zealand
SIGMOD PODS 2024 (International Conference on Management of Data)	June 11 - June 16, 2024- Santiago, Chile
IoT Week (Latest digital developments and trends)	May 07-09, 2024-Dubai, United Arab Emirates

Table 2 List of potential events and conferences where the EXTRACT project can participate

4.3.1. Workshops

Below is a list of tentative and non-exhaustive top academic/research venues where the EXTRACT project aims to submit a relevant Workshop proposal which is in line with the research and dissemination strategies and KPIs of the project.

Below is a tentative list of currently identified top academic/research venues where the EXTRACT project could prepare an academic/research/project workshop:

- IEEE International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications (HPCC)
- IEEE International Conference on High Performance Computing, Data & Analytics (HiPC)
- IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)
- International European Conference on Parallel and Distributed Computing (Euro-Par)
- IEEE “Computers, Software & Applications in an Uncertain World” conference (COMPSAC)
- *[Other venues continuously identified]*

As of now, the estimated timeline of completing a workshop is about 6-9 months, considering:

- Identifying the venue (conference, symposium) to co-locate the workshop
- Submitting workshop proposal to the venue
- Getting acceptance for the workshop
- Forming the Technical Program Chair (TPC) and decide Chairs
- Organising and publish the Call for Papers (CFP)
- Performing CFP paper collection and academic peer-review
- Organising and hosting the workshop at the venue
- Publishing the papers and the proceedings of the workshop via open-science channels

4.4. Dissemination register

WP5 has introduced a dissemination register to help partners inform the consortium about their dissemination activities (events, publications, etc). This dissemination register includes the information requested in the dissemination tab in the Participant

Portal and seeks to facilitate the monitoring and reporting of the project's results. The dissemination register has been included in the project's internal repository. Partners are reminded at the monthly Executive Board meetings to add their dissemination activities. The dissemination register representing the activities from the last six months can be found in Annex 1.

5. Community Building and Training Activities

Community building and training are key for ensuring that the EXTRACT technology seizes on opportunities to amplify the dissemination of project results. It also sets the foundation for the future sustainability of the project. As part of task T5.2 Community building and training, WP5 will work to build a community around results. This will be done by regularly providing updated material to relevant stakeholders to maintain their interest in the project. This will take the form of collaboration with fellow EU-projects, engagement via social media, networking during events, and training activities or workshops. Task 5.2 on Community Building and Training will work together with Task 5.4 on Sustainability to seek synergies with relevant stakeholders from both the public and the private sector (see [Section 7](#)).

Synergies will be created with related projects, end users, standardisation bodies and open-source communities. Dedicated trainings or workshops will be organised during the project's lifespan to present results and obtain feedback to validate the EXTRACT approach. Internal and external training courses will be organized to build a common understanding of the different technologies being developed within EXTRACT. Below, we summarise the tentative planning and vision about the efforts that EXTRACT project will apply in order to build the community around EXTRACT as well as to meet its WP5 KPIs.

5.1. Synergies

The EXTRACT project will pursue collaboration with other EU-funded projects, such as those under the same call HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 or those cooperating with the AI4Europe project and its AI-on-Demand Platform (AIoD). Some of these projects have similar topics, but different technologies or focuses, and it will be interesting to open the doors for collaboration in this regard. The EXTRACT project will create a project profile on the AIoD and use its services to help disseminate project results and to share information about trainings.

Since the project's beginning on 1 January 2023, the EXTRACT project has participated in two Big Data Value Association (BDVA) events that have focused on opening communication between players in the European data, and AI R&I realm. These participations included the coordinator's participation in the 'Get to Know' event and a presentation as a panellist at the BDVA [Data Week 23](#) 'Data meets Infrastructure ate

the Edge’. BDVA, as a partner of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership (ADRA) and host of the Data Space Support Centre, offers the EXTRACT project with access to a community of like-minded industry players, researchers, and associations that will be used to raise awareness of the project and its objectives. The EXTRACT project appears on the [‘Liasons and Collaborations’](#) page of this Data Space Support Centre.

5.2. Internal Trainings

WP5 seeks to hold at least one internal training per year to provide all project partners with the opportunity to learn about different technology features and to ensure a common understanding of the different project components. Internal trainings will be related to exploiting the features of the EXTRACT technology. For logistic and budget efficiency, the internal trainings will be hosted online. These trainings will allow partners to obtain a deeper understanding of the different features of the entire EXTRACT technology and to demonstrate the value of these components to other partners who do not have this background.

The envisioned internal Hackathon (see Table 3) will seek to focus on partner institutions (not work packages per se), who will come together to evaluate the technology. Ideally, teams of research groups from EXTRACT partners will join together on the occasion of the Hackathon to work out a solution for developing the EXTRACT software platform with the double objective of implementing the platform and training the consortium in different project technologies, thus allowing for a more efficient integration of the developed technologies.

Table 3 EXTRACT project internal training planned for M11-M36

Project Year	Approx. month	Topic	Venue	Duration
1	Nov-Dec 2023	Computing specifics (COMPs, Lithops) and analytic methods required (ML, RL, DL)	Online	1 full day (max 2 days)
2	Nov-Dec 2024	Use-case requirements in terms of computing/analytics	Online	1 full day (max 2 days)
3	Aug-Sep 2025	Internal Hackathon on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Compute Continuum integrations and Use-case specifics – ‘Exascale data’: management (non-tech) + technical challenges and approaches (tech) 	Online	2 full day (max 3 days)

5.3 External Trainings

If and when feasible and applicable, the matured internal trainings will be offered as external trainings to promote EXTRACT technology and for general dissemination and community building. The tentative planning of such external trainings will be performed once each internal training is completed and delivered, and the project partners reach consensus on the organisation and feasibility of providing these external trainings. External trainings may include participation in workshops, hackathons or tutorials.

External trainings would begin in year two, beginning with an external Hackathon at the BSC in Spring 2024, followed by a workshop in Autumn 2024 and ending with a tutorial, once the EXTRACT technology has reached some maturity in month 33.

Although the initial description of action (DOA) identifies a summer school as part of the external training, the consortium believes that an 'EXTRACT Hackathon' would be more feasible and have a larger impact on the target community, mainly the research and industrial community. The BSC would host the Hackathon. Its reputation as a supercomputing hub and its infrastructure would facilitate the logistics of attracting and hosting participants and providing this type of training.

The decision to change the summer school for a Hackathon does not mean that the project will not have a presence in such venues. Partners are still encouraged to take part in seasonal schools to share their knowledge and build a community around the EXTRACT project. For example, partner BINARE will participate in the CSC Summer School in High Performance Computing 2023, where it aims to: 1) encourage uptake of cutting-edge HPC programming and computing knowledge and experience with top HPC systems (e.g., LUMI in Finland is Top3 globally and Top1 in Europe); 2) use that venue and opportunity to disseminate information about EXTRACT and thus contribute to the community building efforts; 3) collect experience and insights about summer school organisation and logistics that may help EXTRACT's External Hackathon event.

Overall, the community building and training task is well on its way to engaging with potential stakeholders who will be able to benefit from EXTRACT technology. The synergy and training plans set the direction for month 6-month 36 of the project and provide the foundation for the creation of a resilient and relevant community.

6. Initial Exploitation Plan

The term 'exploitation' is defined under the Horizon Rules for Participation as follows: 'Each beneficiary must – up to four years after the period set out in [GA] Article 3 - take measures aiming to ensure "exploitation" of its results by: (a) using them in further research activities; (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process; (c) creating and providing a service, or (d) using them in standardisation activities.'

Exploitation activities have a broader scope compared to communication and dissemination. They can include actions such as using the project results in research activities that go beyond those covered by the concerned project; developing, creating and marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service; etc. The main

goal of the exploitation plan is to make use of the results for societal, scientific, financial, and other purposes.

The project partners are the first to exploit the project results themselves, by their own efforts or facilitate exploitation by others (e.g., through making results available under open licenses). This can take place via innovation management actions, copyright management, data management plan and stakeholder/users engagement, among others. Common tools towards these directions are:

- patent applications and publications
- establishment of spin-off or start-up companies
- license practices (open, copyleft)
- use of the results for academic purposes (PhD, post-PhD, follow-up projects)

A series of accompanying tasks should be carried out during the project execution and should be included in the exploitation plan:

- Exploitable Results Identification
- Technological Watch
- Intellectual Property Rights Management
- Market Analysis
- Business Model and Operational Model(s)

Exploitation can only start once the research results are available. It focuses on making concrete use of research results for commercial, societal, policy, and other purposes. Depending on the nature and scope of the project, there is a wide spectrum of results that may be recognised as exploitable, including policy recommendations or standardisation activities.

Each beneficiary must take measures that aim to ensure the exploitation of their results, either by themselves (e.g., for further research or for commercial or industrial exploitation in its own activities) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties, e.g., through licensing or by transferring the ownership of results). Beneficiaries must be proactive and take specific measures to ensure that their results are used (to the extent possible and justified). However, exploitation does not necessarily need to be undertaken directly by the participants. They are entitled to choose that it be done by another entity. Such indirect exploitation can be performed by licensing the results or assigning them to third parties as well as providing open access, in accordance with the requirements established in the grant agreement and the consortium agreement.

In the EXTRACT project, all project partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation to foster and ensure awareness and transfer results for the highest possible impact.

6.1. Preliminary Plan for Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The first step for developing the appropriate and comprehensive Exploitation Plan is to identify the early-on the list of most likely Key Exploitable Results (KERs) being developed during the EXTRACT project.

- Copyright software implementation?
- Patents being drafted?
- Trademarks?
- Designs?

At this stage, there is early bootstrap work inside the consortium that aims for each partner to identify most likely KERs that apply to their particular developments and contributions.

6.2. Preliminary Exploration of Tools for Exploitation of KERs

To identify and to exploit KERs in a most efficient and effective manner, the current plan is to use a set of existing exploitation, KER and IPR tools that are most commonly used for such activities. Below we summarize the main tools currently identified for upcoming exploitation of KERs and IPR:

- Patent search tools
- Trademark search tools
- Patent, design and trademark analysis and search services
- EUIPO 'SME Fund' - funding, tools, instruments and services for SMEs for IPR protection
 - EU: <https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en/online-services/sme-fund>
- National Patent Offices funding, tools, instruments and services for SMEs for IPR protection
 - Finland: <https://www.businessfinland.fi/en/for-finnish-customers/services/funding/research-and-development/innovation-voucher>
 - France: in exploration phase
 - Israel: in exploration phase
 - Italy: in exploration phase
 - Spain: in exploration phase
 - Switzerland: Swiss SMEs receiving funding from the Swiss Innovation agency can benefit from IPR management services, in cooperation with the Swiss Federal Institute of Intellectual Property. The two bodies mainly offer expertise in patent search, and patent landscape analysis. For more advanced projects, additional IPR management tools are offered, such as registration of a trademark, advanced patent search, and development of an IP strategy, licensing. More information can be found [here](#).

7. Initial Sustainability Vision

Even though the task exploring the sustainability of EXTRACT (T5.4) starts in month 16 (i.e., after the official deadline of this deliverable), WP5 nevertheless briefly introduces the vision that underpins EXTRACT project's sustainability efforts, aims and concrete steps.

In this task, **sustainability** refers to the exploitation of results after the end of the project. Task 5.4 will rely both on the results of the project, and on the work of Task 5.2 *Building communities*, to make recommendations on results' exploitation after M36.

The project will design and develop specific data-mining frameworks for data with extreme characteristics (huge amount, real-time processing, etc.).

Firstly, it foresees exploiting these frameworks as software applications to be sold over a dedicated marketplace, one data-mining framework being specific to one 'type' of use case. The marketplace would then sell at least one application generating Personalized Evacuation Routes in Venice, but also in other cities, and another one focusing on the processing and filtering of raw data.

To build this application store, partners will leverage the expertise of SixSq in selling business applications, designed to run at the edge and/or in the cloud, on the Nuvla Marketplace. An exploratory phase around the marketplace platform and functionalities will give partners time to imagine what the EXTRACT marketplace could look like. This dedicated marketplace can be hosted by Nuvla, as a spin-off.

Secondly, in cooperation with Task 5.2, EXTRACT will seek synergies with relevant stakeholders from both the public and the private sector. First steps will consist of identifying the most relevant bodies to involve (thanks to a target mapping) and activities to organise (workshops, webinars organisation) to start looking for collaborations. The project will also build on existing partnerships or synergies that partners may have with relevant bodies.

These collaborations will be key in identifying and addressing real present needs, predict future ones, and help partners to identify new business use cases. It is intended that partners will continue to collaborate with each other to address these use cases after the end of the project.

A third track will focus on the acceptability of the project's achievements by the business world. It will especially assess the IPR management, procedures for joint exploitation agreements and the use of Open-Source communities for promotion.

The ideas above and first outcomes will be further described in the first version of the *Sustainability plan of results*, due in month 15.

8. Evaluation of Dissemination and Communication Performance

All dissemination, communication and exploitation activities will be carefully monitored to measure their effectiveness. Quality metrics will be examined, and BIN, as leader of WP5, will regularly assess dissemination progress to ensure swift action is taken, if necessary. The quantitative indicators are defined in Table 5. These KPIs represent a means of monitoring the direction and success of the dissemination, exploitation and sustainability activities and the consortium will strive to go beyond these indicators to the best of its abilities and as far as permitted by the research, innovation and marketing contexts.

Activity	KPI (by end of the project)	Measure
Corporate image	Logo and poster creation	1 PPT, Word, and poster template
Website	Visitor statistics (unique visitors)	3000 sessions (average 1000 sessions per year)
Social media	Number of twitter followers and LinkedIn group members	<p>At least 250 Twitter -> updated to 150 Twitter</p> <p>At least 150 LinkedIn -> updated to 250 LinkedIn</p> <p><i>NB: after carefully analysing the capabilities (e.g., events, groups, material sharing) and audiences (wider presence, more professional and research presence) of both platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter), we came to the conclusion that LinkedIn is more suitable and efficient for EXTRACT than Twitter, therefore we take the opportunity of this first D5.1 deliverable to swap the targeted KPIs, following the above motivation.</i></p>
Promotional material	Flyers, posters, Project videos	<p>At least 2 posters/infographic</p> <p>At least 3 Project videos</p>
Press strategy	Number of press releases/ press clippings	<p>3 press releases (one press release /year)</p> <p>At least 25 press clippings</p>

Event participation	Key notes, organized events with significant attendance (more than 30 ppl)	At least 2 keynotes, at least one organized event, at least one booth in an industrial event
Publications	Papers in conferences and journals	At least 4 publications per year
Training courses	Organisation of internal training courses for Project partners and participation in external trainings such as summer schools, tutorials, workshops	1 internal training course per year At least 1 workshop, 1 tutorial and 1 summer school
Final event	Organisation of a final Project event	Significant attendance 50 or more

Table 4 EXTRACT project dissemination, community building, exploitation and sustainability key project indicators

9. Conclusion

The communication, dissemination, exploitation and community building activities defined in this document will be carefully monitored throughout the life of the project. The project KPIs provide a clear measure of whether the plan is going as expected or if it requires adjustment given any unexpected opportunities or challenges that may arise. The plan detailed above provides a strong foundation, which will be built on in the coming months. It ensures that the consortium is aware of the dissemination tools and channels available to it, and the forthcoming training and exploitation needs.

Importantly, the plan identifies key target audiences and messages that will help partners understand their audience more clearly and thus help tailor the messages of the project to different scenarios and audiences, which will be essential for uptake and action down the road.

The plan will be monitored continuously and will be followed by D5.2 Updated dissemination, exploitation and community building, and first sustainability report, which will describe the activities performed until month 15, and establish new objectives and actions if necessary. A final deliverable, D5.3 Final dissemination, exploitation, community building and sustainability report will be prepared at the end of the project, detailing the activities performed in the last period and the activities in progress that will ensure sustainability.

10. Acronyms and abbreviations

- ADRA – AI, Data and Robotics Association
- AI – Artificial Intelligence
- BDVA – Big Data Value Association
- BE – British English
- BIN – BINARE
- BSC – Barcelona Supercomputing Center
- D – deliverable
- DoA – Description of Action (Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)
- EXTRACT – A distributed data-mining software platform for extreme data across the compute continuum
- EB – Executive Board
- EC – European Commission
- EOSC – European Open Science Cloud
- HE – Horizon Europe
- HPC – High Performance Computing
- IPR – Intellectual Property Right
- KER – Key Exploitable Result
- KPI – Key Performance Indicator
- M – Month
- ML– Machine Learning
- SIXSQ – Six Square
- SME – Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
- STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Math
- WP – Work Package
- 8M – Eight of March, International Women’s Day

11. Annex 1: Dissemination Register

EXTRACT Dissemination Register (activities)						
No	Type of dissemination activity	Date	Details	Target audience reached	Goal of dissemination activity and relation to WP/T	Comment
1	Non-scientific publication	15/01/2023	Distributing computations across the continuum opens up huge possibilities	HiPEAC European network on high performance embedded architecture and complication	Connect the EXTRACT project goals with those of HiPEAC audiences	Elli Kartsakli (BSC)
2	Project LinkedIn account launched	15/01/2023	EXTRACT EU Project	General public, academic, industry, policymakers	Provide a contact point for the project, create a forum for exchange and to share updates	ALL
3	Project Twitter account launched	15/01/2023	@EXTRACT_EU_proj	General public, academic, industry, policymakers	Provide a contact point for the project, create a forum for exchange and to share updates	ALL
4	Workshop	23/02/2023	Get-to-know" introductory workshop and welcome day to HE Data projects (WP2021-22)	Fellow projects-HE Cluster 4 – Destination 3 WP2021-22	Present mission and objectives. Identify expected contributions to European Common Data Spaces. Identify collaboration opportunities among DSSC projects	Eduardo Quiñones (BSC)
5	Non-scientific publication	26/02/2023	Binare Platform for (I)IoT/Embedded Security, Electronics Today Feb 2023	Electronics component industry	Reach industry to discuss cybersecurity and ongoing EU projects where Binare is contributing	1 page infographic (BIN)
6	Project website launch	28/02/2023	https://extract-project.eu/	General public, academic, industry, policymakers	Announce the project's launch and raise awareness of the project	ALL

7	Press release	03/03/2023	Horizon Europe project EXTRACT kicks off with a holistic approach to extreme data across the compute continuum	General public, academic, industry, policymakers	To raise awareness of the project through the technical media and to draw attention to the website launch	ALL
8	Meeting	08/03/2023	Presentation of EU projects to T-Systems	Industry	Internal presentation of EXTRACT project	URV
9	Meeting	15/03/2023	Presentation of EU projects to Arsys	Industry	Internal presentation of EXTRACT project	URV
10	Meeting	21/03/2023	Presentation of EU projects to Telefonica Research	Industry	Internal presentation of EXTRACT project	URV
11	Non-scientific publication	Submitted 28/03/2023	IoT-Edge-Cloud: building a simple, secure, and future proof infrastructure	HiPEAC European network on high performance embedded architecture and complication	Industry perspective on edge computing within the context of EU projects, with a focus on EXTRACT importance for compute continuum edge-focus	SIXSQ
12	Technical Blog	20/04/2023	Run Scalable GPU Workloads on IBM Cloud VPC with Ray and CUDA	ITNEXT.io (>52K followers) - devs, it admins, it managers, etc	Tooling and insights for deploying scalable GPU workloads in IBM Cloud VPC with Ray	Erez Hadad (IBM)
13	Technical Blog	20/04/2023	Get VMs with CUDA and other features on IBM Cloud VPC - Easily!	ITNEXT.io (>52K followers) - devs, it admins, it managers, etc	Easy image customization in #ibmcloud VPC	Erez Hadad (IBM)
14	Presentation at a conference	09/05/2023	EXTRACT-TASKA: orchestration, data	Members of the International Virtual	Present TASKA use case to experts in the field	Baptiste Cecconi (ObsParis)

			mining and decision making in radio astronomy	Observatory Alliance		
15	Meeting	12/05/2023	Online Meeting with Xartec Salut to present EU projects	Academic	Internal presentation of the EXTRACT project and ask for collaboration with dissemination	URV
16	Panelist in a conference	14/06/2023	Building a Cognitive Cloud-Edge Continuum for Next-Generation Data Processing Applications	BDVA-hosted DATA Week brings together EU projects, industry and research experts	Share project with Cloud-Edge-IoT community, explore synergies between ongoing Research and Innovation Projects of the Cloud-Edge-IoT community	Andoni Amurrio (IKERLAN)
17	Summer School participation (Community Building)	27/06/2023	CSC Summer School in High-Performance Computing 2023	Early career researchers	Raise awareness of the technology being created as part of the EXTRACT project, train researchers	Binaré (two members participate + disseminate)